

Correlation of experimentally determined lipophilicity with *in silico* blood-brain permeation of new succinimide derivatives

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INTRODUCTION

The blood-brain barrier is a unique, selective barrier formed by the endothelial cells together with perivascular elements. The complex tight junctions between the endothelial cells make the brain practically inaccessible for polar molecules [1]. The application for potential anticonvulsive drug candidates as succinimide derivatives with site of action in the brain parenchyma requires prediction of blood brain permeability in the early stage of drug discovery and development.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

RP HPTLC was used for study of the retention behavior of n-(3- or 4- substituted phenyl)-2-methyl-2-ethylsuccinimide derivatives (Table 1) synthesized on the Faculty of Technology and Metallurgy, University of Belgrade, Serbia. Precoated RP-18W/UV 254 10×10 cm plates (Macherey-Nagel GMBH and Co., Düren, Germany) were used as stationary phase and binary solutions of water with acetonitrile with a varying volume fraction, φ of organic solvent ($\varphi=0.45-0.65$) were the mobile phase. After development, the spots were detected at 254 nm with UV lamp and R_f values were measured. Software package i-lab 2.0 (<https://ilab.acdlabs.com/iLab2/>) was applied for determining the molecular characteristics of the compounds observed as well as their *in silico* predicted logarithm of blood brain barrier permeability.

RESULTS

The R_M value obtained from reversed-phase thin-layer chromatography, which was calculated as:

$$R_M = \log (R_f^{-1} - 1) \quad Eq. (1)$$

depends linearly on the volume fraction, φ of organic modifier in the mobile phase:

$$R_M = R_M^0 + S \times \varphi \quad Eq. (2)$$

Where R_M^0 (intercept) is the extrapolated value corresponding to $\varphi = 0\%$ of the organic modifier, and S is the slope of the linear plot. The retention constants, R_M^0 reflect the lipophilicity of the observed compounds.

Table 1. The structure of the compounds analyzed

Clark proposes a simple guidance concerning the molecular properties that favor brain permeation [2]:

- The sum of nitrogen and oxygen (N + O) atoms should be less than 5.
- The difference ClogP - (N + O) should be positive.
- The polar surface area (PSA) of the compound should be below 90 Å² according to van de Waterbeemd, or according to Kelder less than 60–70 Å².
- The molecular weight (MW) should be kept below 450.
- A logD value in the range 1–3 is recommended.

All compounds observed violate at least one Clark's rule (Table 2). Compounds 4 and 7 which have as functional groups –COOH and –NO₂ respectively and may have limited permeation in the brain unless transporters are not involved in their active transport in the brain parenchyma. More hydrophobic compounds are prone to permeate in CNS easily, while polar molecules have restricted permeation.

Compound	N+O	ClogP-(N+O)	PSA	MW	logD	Number of violated rules
1	3	-1.47	37.38	271.26	1.11	1
2	4	-3.14	57.61	233.26	0.79	2
3	4	-2.38	46.61	247.29	1.21	1
4	5	-3.41	74.68	261.27	-2.25	3
5	4	-2.39	61.17	242.27	0.97	2
6	3	-0.97	37.38	231.29	1.43	1
7	6	-4.13	86.21	262.26	1.00	3
8	3	-0.48	37.38	251.71	1.65	1
9	3	-0.33	37.38	296.16	1.81	1
10	3	-0.48	37.38	251.71	1.91	1
11	3	-0.33	37.38	296.16	1.99	1

Table 2. Physical-chemical properties of the compounds analyzed according to Clark's rules

Compounds with acidic properties which are ionized in physiological pH do not cross the blood brain barrier [3]. For this set of observed compounds, *in silico* predicted \log_{BBB} (i-lab 2.0) was positively associated with experimentally obtained lipophilicity quantified with retention constant R_M^0 (Figure 1):

$$\log_{BBB} = -0.299 + 0.148 \times R_M^0 \quad (r^2=0.63; p=0.002).$$

Polarity expressed as polar surface area (PSA) was negatively associated with *in silico* predicted permeation of the analyzed compounds expressed with \log_{BBB} :

$$\log_{BBB} = -0.380 - 0.007 \text{ PSA} \quad (r^2=0.54; p=0.006).$$

The permeation through blood brain barrier for the analyzed compounds could be explained as a combination of both factors, lipophilicity expressed as R_M^0 and polarity quantified as PSA (Figure 2):

$$\log_{BBB} = 0.013 + 0.104 \times R_M^0 - 0.004 \times \text{PSA} \quad (r^2=0.80; p<0.001)$$

Figure 1. Positive association between lipophilicity expressed as retention constant R_M^0 and *in silico* predicted permeation through blood brain barrier for the compounds analyzed.

Figure 2. *In silico* predicted permeation through blood brain barrier for the compounds analyzed depends positively on the lipophilicity and negatively on the polarity

CONCLUSION

The permeation through blood brain barrier for succinimides with polar and acidic functional groups is restricted. The increment of lipophilicity, replacement of acidic functional groups and decrement in polarity, enhances the accessibility of the brain parenchyma for observed succinimides with potential anticonvulsive effects.

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Xanthan–mannitol, a new directly compressible co-processed excipient for controlled release of melatonin

Oral delivery

3D powder bed printing of lactose tablets
3D printed capsules for colon targeted drug delivery
3D Printed Microdevices for Oral Drug Delivery
3D printing of abuse-deterrent and alcohol resistant formulations with modified release properties
A customized screening tool approach for the development of a self-nanoemulsifying drug delivery system (SNEDDS)
A novel carrier for the formulation of amorphous solid dispersion and solubility enhancement of poor water soluble drugs
A systematic approach for assessing the applicability of different types of nasogastric and PEG tubes for the administration of coated pellet formulations
Advantages of Using a Directly Compressible Starch in the Formulation and Scale-up of Ibuprofen Tablets
Application of Artificial Intelligence to Drug Product Development: a Quality-by-Design case study
Application of NUTRIOSE® FB06D, a soluble dextrin, as dry binder in tablets prepared by direct compression
Cellulose nanocrystals: A potential hydrogel drug carrier and nanocomposite for reinforcement of hot melt extrudates
Cochleate nanoparticles for the oral administration of Amphotericin B for leishmaniasis treatment
Compaction Analysis Simplified with the Gamlen Dashboard Software
Compaction behavior of freeze-dried trehalose
Comparison of In Vitro Lipolysis of Bosentan-Loaded Lipid Based Formulations in Fasted State Biorelevant Media
Comparison of the compaction properties of granulated and spray-dried lactose with and without a disintegrant
Compression Profiles of a Directly Compressible Starch using Compaction Simulation and High-Speed Tablet Press
Conversion of Liquid Pharmaceutical Formulations to Powders by using Syloid® XDP Mesoporous Silica Gel
Development and Evaluation of Ready-to-Use Hot Melt Coating / Formulations for Taste Masking
Development and In Vitro Characterization of Bosentan-Loaded Self-Nanoemulsifying Drug Delivery System
Development of structured orodispersible film templates for the improved drug loading in inkjet printing
Direct compression of probiotics: A screening study
Direct cyclodextrin based powder extrusion 3D printing for one-step production of BCS Class II drug loaded tablets
Effect of lipid composition of SLN on oral permeability of a new BCS class IV drug: Witepsol® versus Gelucire®
Effect of Simulated Intestinal Media Composition on Solubility and Permeability of Cinnarizin, Dipyridamole and Fenofibrate
Emulsification speed of amphiphilic starches

Encapsulation method for oral delivery of a complex mixture of microorganisms

Enhanced Loading Efficiency and Mucoadhesion Properties of Gellan Gum Thin Films by Complexation with Hydroxypropyl- β -Cyclodextrin

EVA as a matrix excipient for personalized 3D printed tablets using HME and FDM

Evaluation of Partially Pregelatinized Starch in a Continuous High Shear Wet Granulation Process

Exploratory study of Aripiprazole-Adipic acid Cocrystals produced by Hot Melt Extrusion Techniques for improved Solubility and Dissolution rate

Fabrication of ondansetron 3D printed orally disintegrating printlets (ODP) via selective laser sintering

Flow Properties, Morphology and Compression Characteristics of a Directly Compressible Starch Before and After Feeding through Loss in Weight Continuous Feeder

Formulation and characterization of tablets with dry birch leaves extract

Formulation of essential oil tablets through microencapsulation and subsequent compression

Formulation of orodispersible carbamazepine/hydroxypropyl- β -cyclodextrin tablets with five-in-one high functionality excipients for direct compression

Formulation of tablets containing mesoporous silica nanoparticles loaded with pramipexole

Furosemide: In vitro modified-release studies from ulvan tablets

How do Orodispersible Tablets Behave in an In Vitro Oral Cavity Model

Impact of glycerol on the coil/helix transition of gelatin and the viscoelastic behavior of soft capsule shell formulations

Impact of phospholipids on Prediction of Solubility Limited Fraction Absorbed in Physiologically Based Biopharmaceutics Modelling

Impact of Surface Properties of Core Material on the Stability of Hot Melt Coated Multiparticulate Systems

Improving treatment in maple syrup urine disease patients with personalized isoleucine printlets (3D printed tablets)

In vitro models of the intestinal mucosa for testing anti-inflammatory nanomedicine

In vitro Permeability Comparison of HPC-based Itraconazole Nanosuspensions

Influence of anaesthesia and capsule size in the gastric emptying of non-disintegrating capsules in rats

Influence of binder critical material attributes of hydroxypropyl cellulose in high-shear mixing

Influence of the cooling regime on the gel elasticity of soft gelatin capsule shell formulations

In-use Stability Improvement of the Moisture Sensitive Drug Ranitidine HCl Through Excipient Selection
In-use Stability Improvement of the Moisture Sensitive Drug Ranitidine HCl Through Excipient Selection

Investigation of the Impact of Formulation and Processing Conditions on Drug Release from An Aqueous Ethylcellulose Dispersion

MicroCoatTM for the development of Sustained Release Fixed Dose Combination Products in Microparticle-Filled Straw for Patients with Dysphagia

Microcontainers protect the prodrug valaciclovir from degradation in the intestinal environment

Mitigation of Sensitive API Degradation through Lipid-based Formulation and Soft Gelatin Capsule

Mucus-permeating nanocarriers for oral delivery of insulin. From in vitro to in vivo

Novel approach to treat genotype-specific hypertension using a riboflavin/amlodipine polypill

Novel authentication technology using molecular tags as a PCID in solid oral dosage forms

Oral administration of Dalargin: Improvement of peptide stability by cyclodextrin grafted ammonium chitosan

Pharmaceutical development of an orally disintegrating tablets of carbamazepine using the SeDeM diagram tool

Physico-chemical alterations of saliva caused by radiation therapy in head and neck area

Polymeric-based nanocarriers: a study of their mucus permeating properties

Preparation of multiple-unit tablets containing enteric-coated pellets with diclofenac sodium using novel calcium-phosphate-based starter pellets

Production of Different Nanoemulsions with High Energy Method for Oral Drug Delivery

Scaled-up production and tableting of grindable electrospun fibers containing an oral antisense oligonucleotide

Scaled-up solid formulation of living anaerobic bacteria for oral delivery using electrospinning

Stereolithography (SLA) 3D printing of an antihypertensive polyprintlet: Case study of an unexpected photopolymer-drug reaction

Study of Formulation and Manufacturing of Fixed dose Combination ER and Glipizide IR Bilayer Tablets

Tablet formulation studies with co-processed excipients for direct compression

The influence of filament composition on the properties of 3D printed tablets with bicalutamide

Understanding the Physical Chemistry of the Buffering Action by Bicarbonate: Prospects in Enteric-Coated Dosage Form Development

Use of pea starch maltodextrins in nutraceutical formulations

Pediatric and geriatric drug delivery

3D printed orodispersible films loaded with a thermosensitive and bitter drug substance

Acceptability of a sublingual drug formulation for respiratory tract infections in children aged 3 to 5 years

Adherence and acceptability of an oral antibiotic used for the prevention of pediatric urinary tract infection in Japan

Characterization of micro-extrusion 3D printing for the production of dose homogeneous paediatrics orodispersibles PrintletsTM

Development of Compartmental Films for Simplified Administration

Development of orodispersible films as dosage forms for pediatric patients

Extrudate materials via hot melt extrusion mask the bitter taste of drugs used for neglected tropical diseases

Fixed-Dose Combination coated mini-tablets designed for the management of GERD in paediatric patients

Hydroxypropyl-beta-cyclodextrin as a multifunctional excipient in orodispersible films

Rapid Dissolving Capsules for the Administration of Enteric Coated Prednisolone Microparticles

Review of methods for TPMT biomarker genotyping in the personalisation of thiopurine therapy

Safety and Efficacy characteristics of pharmacists recommended medications for paediatric patients

Technological approaches for extemporaneous preparation of oral pediatric formulations with sildenafil citrate

Regulatory affairs

A National System for Medical Device Incident Reporting

Defining a strategy for successful compliance to the new Medical Device Regulation

Drug utilization research on medication adherence: a case of fixed versus free combination of antihypertensive drugs

Facilitating patient access to quality medicines: Associations between USP Monograph Standards, ANDA Approval and Prescription Drug Costs

Medical Devices Directive in the European Union adapting to the EU Regulations

Medicinal substances meet medical devices: Drug-Device Combinations and their neighbours

Perception of Rare Diseases and Orphan Medicines

Perspectives in quality control of cannabis for medicinal purposes

Regulatory Science Research in Pharmacovigilance - The Experience of the Malta Medicines Authority

The impact of the pharmaceutical legislation on market penetration of biosimilar drugs: a drug utilization study

Technical Innovations

A new method to produce high-dose loaded dissolving microarray patches

Gentle Drying for Probiotic Products

Inhibition of bacterial biofilm formation in biomedical device after poly(methylmethacrylate)-co-dimethylacrylamide plus silver nanoparticles coating

Simultaneous estimation of naltrexone and bupropion hydrochloride in a binary mixture using UV spectrophotometry

The ISOLPHARM project: proof of concept of no-carrier added radioisotopes production and development of innovative radioconjugate for cancer therapy

Track-and-Trace: Novel Anti-Counterfeit Measures using Combined 2D-3D Printing Technologies

Veterinary

In-vitro evaluation of organogel based systems for veterinary use

Production, characterization, and in vitro efficacy of canine and equine lyo-secretome injectable formulation in regenerative medicine

POSTER SESSION ON FRIDAY, 14 MAY 2021

Bioavailability and absorption enhancement

Absorption profile of oleocanthal in rats

Amorphous solid dispersions of cannabidiol with an increase of the aqueous solubility: influence of the carrier, the hot melt extrusion parameters and the use of a crystallization inhibitor

Correlation of experimentally determined lipophilicity with in silico blood-brain permeation of new succinimide derivatives

Development of prednisolone containing in situ gelling ophthalmic formulations

Effect of 2-hydroxypropyl- β -cyclodextrin on the solubility and permeability of psoralen and 5-methoxypsoralen

Effect of carrier type and surfactant concentration on the silymarin release

Evaluation of potential of amino acids for amorphization and dissolution improvement of carvedilol

Exploring NSAIDs bioavailability through THEDES-like liquid formulations

Fraction of Drug Absorbed Predicted from In Vitro Flux Measurements

Impact of mucoadhesive polymeric nanoparticles containing thermosensitive hydrogels on transcorneal administration of 5-fluorouracil

Improvement of fenofibrate aqueous solubility by using mesoporous silica impregnation under pressurized carbon dioxide

Improving the bioavailability of anti-tuberculosis drugs through deep eutectic systems

Influence of pharmaceutical polymers on the recrystallization and dissolution of nimodipine

Influence of the luminal perfusion rate in the determination of the effective intestinal permeability coefficient of levofloxacin

Marinosolv: A novel solubilization technology

Mesoporous silica: a solution for amorphous stabilization of poor glass formers

Microenvironmental pH-modified solid dispersions for improving dissolution rate of valsartan

Microwave-induced in situ amorphization: mechanistic studies and application in indomethacin solid dispersion

Novel biphasic lipolysis testing of nilotinib lipid based suspensions to predict in vivo performance

Permeability and biocompatibility evaluation of olopatadine hydrochloride viscous ophthalmic solutions using in vitro 3D corneal model

Predicting the performance of amorphous solid dispersions

Semi-volatile solvent mixtures: a novel approach to liquisolid systems preparation

Solid lipid nanocarriers to increase oral bioavailability of the peptide Leuprolide

Spray drying of amorphous solid dispersions (ASD): small scale screening of batches containing less than 50 mg API

Structural Dynamics and Diffusion in Solid Dispersions

Synthesis of Novel Esters of Ciprofloxacin as Prodrugs for Improved Activity

Synthesis, physicochemical, biopharmaceutical and antimicrobial characterisation of Gatifloxacin n-butanoate, Gatifloxacin iso-butanoate and their ionic liquid salts as prodrugs for ocular drug delivery

Buccal and nasal delivery

Application of a Thermosensitive In Situ Gel of Chitosan-Based Nasal Spray Loaded with Tranexamic Acid for Localised Treatment of Nasal Wounds

Cytokine mediated inflammation in the oral cavity: Consequences on drug delivery

Design of Dextran Sulfate/Poly-L-lysine Nanogel for Ovalbumin delivery

Development of matrix for freeze-dried buccal vaccines

Development of mucoadhesive carrier systems for flavoring agents

Drug delivery strategies of Geraniol via nose-to-brain for the treatment of neuronal disorders

Formulation of *Cardiospermum halicacabum* extract loaded vesicles for nasal delivery.

In vitro release methodologies for nasal powder testing

Orodispersible films: A delivery platform for solid lipid nanoparticles?

Self-assembly multilayer films for buccal drug delivery: the impact of polymer cross-linking

Soluble Idebenone/Hydroxypropyl-B-Cyclodextrin Inclusion Complex for nasal administration

In vivo - in vitro correlations

A microfluidic human cornea model with dynamic dilution profile for in vitro drug absorption studies

Cryopreservation using Natural Deep Eutectic Systems: A new tool for pharmaceutical applications

Development of in vitro methods to evaluate the bitter taste using extra-oral bitter receptors

Direct visualizing of immediate release tablet disintegration; in vivo and in vitro studies

Formulation development of Telmisartan driven by flux measurements

In quest of a suitable tool to assess drug and nanomedicine penetration into tumor spheroids

Towards enabling IVIVC for orally inhaled products: PBPK modelling in dry powder inhaler development

Usefulness of small scale biphasic dissolution experiments in estimating precipitation rates for input in PBPK modelling

Pharmaceutical manufacturing and engineering

3D nanofibrous scaffolds for tendon reconstruction

3D printing of personalized bioresorbable airway stents

3D Printing of tablets via fused deposition modeling - Focus on filament production

3D-printing of suppositories based on hard fat

A mixture design approach to optimizing spray-dried sericin-based formulations

An existing polymer reinvented: A new particle designed polyvinyl alcohol for coating applications

Analysis and optimization of a pharmaceutical production process by computer simulation

Applying optical coherence tomography during film coating development

- Cellulosic dry binders in direct compression and roll compaction: effect of particle size and mechanical properties on tablet performance
- Characterization and modeling of the viscoelasticity of pharmaceutical tablets
- Characterizing powders flowability and triboelectric behavior for continuous manufacturing applications
- Comparison of artificial neural networks and response surface methodology for efficient extraction of rosmarinic acid from *Satureja kitaibelii*
- Comparison of the robustness of pellet film coating with and without in-process coating thickness evaluation
- Continuous small batch OSD production @ 9σ level
- Correlation study between SeDeM diagram expert system tool and the rotary press simulator Styl'ONE applied to a Zidovudine's direct compression industrial tablets formulation.
- Developing a framework to acquire the Rp-distribution of a spin-freeze dried product
- Development of a spray dried enteric release form of essential oil prepared by co-spray drying polysaccharides and methacrylate.
- Development of flow cell for in-situ visualization of dissolution processes in solid dosage forms
- Direct compression of QESD crystallized metformin hydrochloride into high-drug-loaded tablets
- Directly compressible spray dried powders obtained by dry coating using pharmaceutical mills
- DoE Combined with Process Automation: a New Approach to Quality by Design
- Does Tableability Really Improve With Decreased Diameters of Tablet Punches?
- Downstream processing of co-amorphous olanzapine
- Effect of binder type and lubrication method on the binder efficacy for direct compression
- Effect of dry ball milling process on curcumin crystals and its impact on physico-chemical and biopharmaceutical properties
- Effect of exposure time on dimensional accuracy and dissolution rate of printlets fabricated with DLP 3D printer
- Elastic properties of various Lactose grades during compaction, evaluated by ultrasonic-measurement system KIM
- Enhancement of nifedipine solubility in supercritical carbon dioxide: role of co-solvents
- Estimation of material hold-up in twin-screw granulation
- Evaluation of dry granulation and tableting for a formulation with a high amount of herbal drug using Design of Experiment
- Evaluation of hydroxypropyl cellulose (HPC) for aqueous-based film coating system
- Fluidized and Spouted Bed for the preparation of directly processable amorphous solid dispersions
- Formation of delta-mannitol by co-spray drying to enhance tableability of paracetamol-mannitol formulations
- Formulation and Characterization of Dissolvable PLGA-Loaded Microneedles for Ocular Drug Delivery
- Formulation by design (FbD) applied for the identification of Critical Quality Attributes (CQAs) in process manufacturing of chitosan/glycosaminoglycan electrospun scaffolds
- Formulation of Microorganisms to Tablets: How Different Process Steps Influence the Microbial Viability
- How to improve dies loading when using poor flowable powders
- Impact of incorporated APIs on material properties of hot-melt extruded amorphous solid dispersions

- Impact of magnesium stearate and sodium starch glycolate on work of compaction, detachment and ejection stress of microcrystalline cellulose
- Induced Jet Decay from Flow-Channel Streams
- Influence of binder attributes on binder effectiveness in a continuous twin screw wet granulation process via wet and dry binder addition
- Influence of degree of disorder on the inter-particulate bonding of lactose particles
- Influence of Mesoporous Silica (MPS) on Flow and Tribo-electrostatic Charging during Manufacturing
- Influence of Residence Time in Manufacturing Amorphous Solid Dispersions via Hot Melt Extrusion
- Inline Characterization of Dispersive Mixing Properties in Twin Screw Extrusion
- Investigation of a Model for Mixing Capacity in a Rotary Tablet Press
- Investigation of different mannitol grades and their performance on a dosing-disc capsule filling machine
- Investigation of the Dissolution Behavior of APIs for the Description of Inherent Solubility Properties
- Investigation on the dustiness of a binary powder mixture with a newly developed two-chamber setup
- Linking raw material characteristics and process settings to granule CQAs in continuous twin screw granulation
- Liquid Carbon Dioxide for the Production of Small Droplets
- Liquisolid systems with mesoporous silica based carriers: An investigation of flow and compaction properties
- Manufacture of amorphous solid dispersions by spray drying using a coaxial three-fluid nozzle
- Medications with novel 3D printed tactile patterns for patients with visual impairment
- Microfluidics and pharmaceutical devices by 3D printing
- Mind the Gap – Importance of Particle Distance During Drying of API-Nanosuspensions in a Fluidized Bed Process
- Next Generation Lipid-Based Excipients: Development of dry powders for inhalation via spray drying
- NIR spectroscopy as real time control tool for tablets manufacturing
- Optimization of processing times and temperature for 3D-printing of tablets
- Particle agglomeration analysis using PATVIS APA and deep learning
- Performance of anhydrous lactose in roller compaction
- PLGA nanoparticles manufacturing : comparison of ultrasound based production method
- Powder vs. granules – material characterization of binary powder blends and roller compacted granules for oral solid dosage forms
- Prediction of tablet weight variability based on process parameters and blend properties
- Preparation and characterization of electrospun polycaprolactone (PCL) tubular scaffolds for bioengineering of small-diameter blood vessels
- Preparation of Submicron Particles via Spray Drying using Ultrasonic Nebulization and Electrostatic Precipitation
- Printability of paracetamol-PCL filaments in FDM 3D process
- Processability of poly(vinyl alcohol) filaments prepared by hot melt extrusion for fused deposition modelling 3D printing
- Production and characterization of Polydioxanone (PDO) fibers by centrifugal spinning for biomedical application

Production of Drug Nanocrystals Engineered using a High Throughput Microfluidic Reactor

Raman Microscopy of Low-dose Filaments For 3D Printing

Rational design of solvent-based ASD production processes

Spray Drying versus Freeze Drying of cytokines exemplified by the model protein CXCL8

Spray Flash Evaporation and its extension for the submicronization of Active Pharmaceutical Ingredients

Synthesis physicochemical and biopharmaceutical characterization of trimethoxybenzenesulfonamide (TMBS)- a new derivative of gallic acid

Tabletability of Oil-loaded Powders

Tackling ASD Flowability: Optimization in Downstream Processing

Tacrolimus suppositories prepared by semisolid-extrusion 3D printing for the treatment of Inflammatory Bowel Disease

The effect of lactose particle size on the tablet strength - compaction pressure relationship

The impact of suction pressure on die filling on rotary presses

The influence of lower punch vibration on the compactability and bondability of different types of microcrystalline cellulose

The role of online content uniformity measurement in the rapid automated process development of a continuous production system used for direct-filling hard gelatin capsules

Twin-screw granulation: An attempt for a quantitative description of screw configuration impact

Using microfluidics for the development of chitosan nanogels for gene therapy

Physical pharmacy

3D printed capsules for modulating the sustained release rate from a nanocellulose hydrogel

Dissolution in Intestinal Bicarbonate Buffer: Mass Transport-Dependent Effective pKa and its Implications

Enantiomeric amino acids as co-amorphous systems

Evaluation of Phase Transition of Bicalutamide in Tablets Under Different Storage Conditions

FDM 3D printing of flexible materials for pharmaceutical dosage forms

How Does the Content of Kollidon®VA64 Inhibit the Recrystallization and Improve Dissolution of Ezetimibe from Amorphous Solid Dispersions?

Polymorphism and drug release modification of tristearin-based formulation: the effect of liquid additives

Relationship between particle size and adhesion forces in Neusilin® US2 particles

Solid state amorphization of riboflavin upon milling

Solid state conversion of olanzapine during tableting

Thermal treatment to stabilize/destabilize pharmaceutical glasses

Toward biopredictive dissolution conditions for ionizable BCS class II compounds

Viscosity of ASDs at humid conditions

Preformulation

Assessment of side effects of SMEDDS in the rat

Combination of itraconazole cocrystal and nanocrystal techniques to improve the saturation solubility and dissolution rate

Effect of Maillard reaction on electrospun scaffolds for skin tissue engineering

Electrospun scaffolds in periodontal wound healing

Evaluation of Compressibility Index by SeDeM system method to predict the behavior of some tablets excipients

Evaluation of nephelometric high-throughput method in drug formulation development

Griseofulvin (BCS Class II Drug) Solubilization by Beta Cyclodextrin Derivatives Complexation

Hydrates as a water source for microwave induced in situ amorphization of celecoxib

Hydroxypropyl β Cyclodextrin as a High Efficiency Cholecalciferol Solubilizer

Insights from the preclinical development of Corallopyronin A: Establishing analytical assays for the determination of Corallopyronin A, Corallopyronin isomers and degradation products of stability and bioanalytical samples.

Insights from the preclinical development of Corallopyronin A: Formulation evaluations by physiology-based pharmacokinetics and in vivo predictive in vitro tools

Liquid marbles for bioavailability enhancement of poorly soluble drugs – a case study

Multivariate analysis of powder flow parameters to improve the development of blends for direct compression

Next Generation Lipid-Based Excipients: Solid State - Stability Relationship

Optimization of Bicalutamide-loaded 3D-printing Filament Composition

Oral liquid formulations of carvedilol in medium-chain triglycerides for use in paediatrics

Predicting powder flowability utilizing material characteristics and multivariate approach

Preparation, thermal analysis and phase solubility study of Quercetin inclusion complexes with β -cyclodextrin derivatives

Smart UV: An evolving strategy in sunscreen protection

Studies on modifications of established silk fibroin production methods to enhance protein content

Towards biocompatible formulations of steroids: Preparation of zuranolone nanoformulations

Pulmonary delivery

Activity evaluation of supramolecular compound based on N-acetylcysteine for the treatment of *P. aeruginosa* biofilm

Comparing the mechanical properties of Quali-V®-I and Quali-V®-I Extra Dry capsules for use in dry powder inhalers

Effect of lumen enlargement on functionality of halloysite-chitosan sustained-release nanocontainers

Evaluation of pulmonary and renal tolerance of a cisplatin-based dry powder for inhalation to treat lung cancer

How important is internal lubricant in capsules for inhalation?

Hybrid lipid/polymer nanoparticles for pulmonary delivery of siRNA in cystic fibrosis lung inflammation

In vitro / in vivo Correlation of Two Commercial pMDI Formulations using NGI Analysis with 3D Printed Modified Induction Ports

In vitro Aerodynamic Assessment and Dissolution Profile of Spray-dried Itraconazole Powders for Inhalation from Aqueous Nanosuspensions

In vitro-in silico approach in the assessment of drug deposition and absorption following intratracheal insufflation of an ordered mixture in rats

Novel inhalable redox responsive nanoparticles for the combined treatment of lung cancer

Optimal Carrier Properties For Vaporizing Cannabinoids

Physicochemical factors affecting development of Vancomycin delivery in high dose DPI formulations

Synthesis of rifampicin and pyrazinoic acid biodegradable nanoconjugates for pulmonary delivery

The impact of interaction between inhaled drugs and lung surfactant on in-vitro solubility and predicted in-vivo performance

Stability testing

Cocoa butter and its stability in extemporaneous semisolid formulations

Determination of antioxidant effect of polyols in a cell free environment

DMTA test as an effective rheological alternative for accelerated freeze-thaw stability testing of O/W emulsions

Exploring the Performance and Stability-Controlling Tablet Disintegration Mechanisms

Influence of drug load on the stability of phospholipid-stabilized lipid nanoemulsions

Overcoming The Color Stability Issue Exhibited By Indigo Carmine In Film Coating Formulations

Starting materials

Enzymatically synthesized nanocellulose for drug delivery

GRANFILLER-D® As a New Co-processed Excipient For Orally Disintegrating Tablets Produced by Direct Compression

Pharmaceutical powder tribo-charging: the impact of relative humidity and twin-screw feeding

When CDs Meet DCs: Amphiphilic Cyclodextrin Particles Induce Potent Immune Responses

Chairs and committees

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Co-chairs of the conference

Jörg Breitzkreutz, University of Düsseldorf, Germany

Anna Maria Fadda, University of Cagliari, Italy

Jürgen Siepmann, University of Lille, France

Chair of the programme committee

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Programme

Tuesday, 11 May 2021

13:00 – 13:45	Opening Ceremony	Exhibition
13:45 – 14:45	Key note lecture	
14:45 – 15:15	Coffee break	
15:15 – 17:45	Hot topic lectures	

time zone
CEST

Key note lecture incl. Q&A

Chair: Duncan Craig, University College London

- 13:45 - Engineering cancer immunotherapy
14:45 David J. Mooney, Harvard School of Engineering and Applied Sciences, Cambridge, USA

14:45 - 15:15 Coffee break/exhibition

Hot topic session incl. Q&A

Chairs: Svetlana Ibric, University of Belgrade and Maïke Windbergs, University of Frankfurt

- 15:15 - Digital assistant to support drug product development
16:00 Ferdinand Brandl, BASF, Ludwigshafen, German
- 16:05 - Overcoming challenges of biodegradable drug delivery systems
16:50 Steven Schwendeman, Department of Pharmaceutical Sciences and the Biointerfaces Institute, University of Michigan, Ann Arbor, MI, USA
- 16:55 - Pfizer's „continuous“ journey - Implementing continuous manufacturing into a factory for solid dosage forms
17:45 Clemens Stief, Pfizer, Freiburg, Germany

Wednesday, 12 May 2021

08:45 – 11:15	Invited talks	Short talks	Posters	Exhibition
11:15 – 11:45	Coffee break			
11:45 – 12:15	Award session			
12:15 – 13:15	Plenary lecture			
13:15 – 14:45	Lunch			
14:45 – 17:15	Invited talks	Short talks		

time zone
CEST

Invited talks: Advanced therapeutic products incl. Q&A

Chairs: Karine Andrieux, University Prais Sud and Andreas Zimmer, University of Graz

- 08:45 - Formulation approaches for cell and gene therapies
09:30 Chris Van der Walle, GlaxoSmithKline, Stevenage, United Kingdom
- 09:35 - Comparison of different chromatography-based purification strategies for AAV vectors
09:50 Ruth Rieser, University of Munich, Germany

- 09:50 - Formulation of cationic liposomes enhances the immunogenicity of pDNA vaccine against SARS-COV-2
10:05 Allegra Peletta, ISPSO, University of Geneva, Switzerland
- 10:05 - Question and answer session
10:20 from the two short talks
- 10:25 - Biodrugs and advanced therapy medicinal products: a revolution in medicine
11:10 Maria Luisa Nolli, NCNbio, Milan, Italy

Invited talks: Solid dosage forms incl. Q&A

Chairs: Iris Ziegler, Cordon Pharma and Raphael Wiedey, University of Düsseldorf

- 08:45 - Adoption of the MCS concept in the pharmaceutical industry
09:30 Michael Leane, Bristol-Myers Squibb, New York City, USA/Kendal Pitt, GlaxoSmithKline, Ware, UK
- 09:35 - Process design for innovative drug delivery systems
10:20 Jukka Rantanen, Department of Pharmacy, University of Copenhagen, Denmark
- 10:25 - The importance of understanding the physical and chemical properties of APIs in the digital design of drug products
11:10 Kevin Roberts, Faculty of Engineering, University of Leeds, United Kingdom

Short talks: Controlled drug delivery

Chairs: Werner Weitschies, University of Greifswald and Julijana Kristl, University of Ljubljana

- 08:45 - Design and control of a floating gastroretentive drug delivery system made by hot-melt tube extrusion
09:00 Paul Bebernik, University of Bonn, Germany
- 09:00 - A new calcium oral-controlled-release system based on zeolite for prevention of osteoporosis
09:15 Anna Maria Piras, University of Pisa, Italy
- 09:15 - Question and answer session
09:30
- 09:35 - Spray dried microparticulate drug delivery systems for long-term local osteoarthritis treatment
09:50 Carlota Salgado, University of Geneva, Switzerland
- 09:50 - Tuning the mechanical pore properties and release profile on an antimicrobial peptide from an injectable hydrogel using glycol chitosan
10:05 James Flynn, University of Limerick, Ireland
- 10:05 - Question and answer session
10:20
- 10:25 - Development of N-acetylcysteine-functionalized microcontainers for degradation of biofilm matrix
10:40 Stine Egebro Birk, Technical University of Denmark, Lyngby, Denmark
- 10:40 - SymBiosys® based long acting injectable miroparticle formulations for large proteins
10:55 Tanja Henzler, Merck, Darmstadt, Germany

Programme

10:55 - Question and answer session
11:10

Short talks: Preformulation and bioavailability

Chairs: Catherine Herry, NextPharma and Lea Ann Dailey, University of Vienna

08:45 - In situ drug amorphization using laser irradiation
09:00 Nele-Johanna Hempel, University of Copenhagen, Denmark

09:00 - Understanding the Release of ITZ:HPMCAS
09:15 Amorphous Solid Dispersions
Patrícia Nunes, Hovione, Portugal

09:15 - Question and answer session
09:30

09:35 - Evaluation of different preprocessing methods of
09:50 x-ray micro computed tomography images
Sebastian Bollmann, University of Düsseldorf, Germany

09:50 - Experimental and numerical studies of input
10:05 parameters calibration for the simulation of the
wet granulation process for pharmaceutical use
Maroua Rouabah, Claude Bernard University Lyon 1, France

10:05 - Question and answer session
10:20

10:25 - The Comparison of Permeability Efficacy of
10:40 Olmesartan Medoxomil Lipid Based Drug
Delivery System and Olmesartan Medoxomil
Suspension Formulations by Using Optimized
HDM-PAMPA Model
Yelda Komesli, University of Altinbas, Turkey

10:40 - Insight into amorphous solid dispersion
10:55 dissolution behaviour: laser-diffraction and Raman
spectroscopy holding hands
Maria Paisana, Hovione FarmaCiencia, Lisbon, Portugal

10:55 - Question and answer session
11:10

11:15 - 11:45 Coffee break/exhibition/posters

11:45 - 12:15 APGI award session

Maurice-Marie Janot Award: Robert Langer
APGI Young Investigator Award: Raul Diaz Salmeron
JDDST Best Paper 2020 Award

Plenary lecture incl. Q&A

Chair: Juergen Siepmann, University of Lille

12:15 - Advances in nanotechnology
13:15 Patrick Couvreur, Faculty of Pharmaceutical
Sciences, Paris Sud University, France

13:15 - 14:45 Lunch break/exhibition/posters

Invited talks: What's new in nanotechnology? incl. Q&A

Chairs: Elias Fattal, University Paris Sud and Heike Bunjes, University of Braunschweig

14:45 - What's needed in nanomedicine?
15:30 Twan Lammers, Department Nanomedicines and
Theranostics, RWTH, Aachen University, Germany

15:35 - Nanotechnologies for advanced imaging
16:20 Nathalie Mignet, Chemical and Biological
Technologies for Health, Université de Paris,
France

16:25 - Hyperloaded polymeric micelles for chemo- and
17:10 immunotherapy
Alexander Kabanov, Eshelman School of Pharmacy
at Chapel Hill, University of North Carolina, USA

Invited talks: 3D-printing incl. Q&A

Chairs: Alvaro Goyanes, FabRx and Julian Quodbach, University of Düsseldorf

14:45 - 3D-printing of medicines and implants:
15:30 making the formulations work
Clive Roberts, School of Pharmacy, University of
Nottingham, United Kingdom

15:35 - Thermoplastic copolyesters: A promising
15:50 3D-printing excipient for personalized vaginal
inserts
Martin Spoerk, RCPE, Graz, Austria

15:50 - Semi-Solid Extrusion 3D Printing of
16:05 Orodispersible Films for Veterinary Use
Erica Sjöholm, Abo Academi University, Finland

16:05 - Question and answer session
16:20 from the two short talks

16:25 - 3D-printing in an industrial GMP setting
17:10 Jaedeok Yoo, Aprelia Pharmaceuticals, Blue Ash,
OH, USA

Short talks: Pulmonary, nasal and buccal delivery

Chairs: Ajit Narang, Genetech and Johannes Bartholomäus, PharmaKreativ

14:45 - High potency, brittle matrix tacrolimus powders
15:00 for dry powder for inhalation by thin film freezing
Sawitree Sahakijpijarn, University of Texas at
Austin, USA

15:00 - Delivery of beclomethasone dipropionate
15:15 nanosuspensions via electronic cigarette
Luca Casula, University of Cagliari, Italy

15:15 - Question and answer session
15:30

15:35 - P. aeruginosa biofilm infected bronchial
15:50 epithelium as test-system for anti-infective
aerosol formulations
Claus-Michael Lehr, Saarland University,
Saarbrücken, Germany

15:50 - Evaluation of a novel probiotic nasal spray in
16:05 human volunteers
Filip Kiekens, University of Antwerp, Belgium

16:05 - Question and answer session
16:20

16:25 - Nanofibers with antibiotics and probiotics for the
16:40 two-stage therapy of periodontal disease
Spela Zupancic, University of Ljubljana, Slovenia

16:40 - Mucoadhesive films to elicit nanoparticle buccal
16:55 permeation
Javier Morales, University de Chile, Santiago, Chile

Programme

16:55 - Question and answer session
17:10

Short talks: Tablets and coated tablets

Chairs: Kathrin Bartscher, NextPharma and Rok Dreu, University of Ljubljana

- 14:45 - Profiling the influence of process parameters on the interfacial properties of bilayer tablets
15:00 Jan Hendrik Finke, Technical University of Braunschweig, Germany
- 15:00 - Evaluation of the performance of an external lubrication system implemented in a compaction simulator
15:15 Cedrine de Backere, Ghent University, Ghent, Belgium
- 15:15 - Question and answer session
15:30
- 15:35 - Influence of the unloading conditions on capping and lamination during tableting: numerical and experimental study
15:50 Vincent Mazel, University of Bordeaux, France
- 15:50 - Development of Mini-Tablets with SSR-25
16:05 Valentine Elezaj, University of Düsseldorf, Germany
- 16:05 - Question and answer session
16:20
- 16:25 - High solids film coating systems: continuous vs. batch processing
16:40 Christian Mühlenfeld, Ashland Industries Deutschland GmbH, Düsseldorf, Germany
- 16:40 - Effect of the compaction parameters on the final structure and properties of a press-coated tablet (Tab-in-Tab): experimental and numerical study of the influence of core and shell dimensions
16:55 Léo Picart, University of Bordeaux, France
- 16:55 - Question and answer session
17:10

- 09:35 - Please stay my dear: Interfacial adsorption as driving force for protein particle formation during peristaltic pumping
09:50 Natalie Deiringer, University of Munich, Germany
- 09:50 - Creating Highest Quality L yophilisates With Low Oxygen and Water Content by Smart Polymer Packaging
10:05 Nicole Härdter, University of Munich, Germany
- 10:05 - Question and answer session
10:20 from the two short talks
- 10:25 - Biologics drug product development: challenges at the interface of formulation, primary packaging and application
11:10 Susanne Jörg, Lonza AG, Basel, Switzerland

Invited talks: Localised drug delivery incl. Q&A

Chairs: Carmen Alvarez Lorenzo, University of Santiago de Compostella and Jean Christophe Leroux, ETH Zürich

- 08:45 - Jumping to the brain: tailored nanomedicines
09:30 Giovanni Tosi, University of Modena and Reggio Emilia, Italy
- 09:35 - Development of a dissolution method for dosage forms administered into subtenon space
09:50 Tobias Auel, University of Greifswald, Germany
- 09:50 - Impact of the in vitro release set-up on drug release from PLGA implants
10:05 Celine Bassand, University of Lille, France
- 10:05 - Question and answer session
10:20 from the two short talks
- 10:25 - Inhaled chemotherapy: a new modality for lung cancer treatment?
11:10 Nathalie Wauthoz, Université Libre de Bruxelles, Belgium

Short talks: Nanotechnology

Chairs: Guiseppe De Rosa, University of Naples and Niklas Sandler, Nanoform

- 08:45 - Heterotelechelic polymer prodrug nanoparticles for imaging and combination therapy
09:00 Julien Nicolas, University Paris-Sud, France
- 09:00 - Comparison of Exosome Loading Methodologies – Development of Blood-Brain Barrier-Targeting Exosomes via Dual Asymmetric Centrifugation
09:15 Anne Mahringer, University of Heidelberg, Germany
- 09:15 - Question and answer session
09:30
- 09:35 - Antiangiogenic folate-targeted nanoparticles for docetaxel delivery in ovarian cancer
09:50 Claudia Conte, University of Naples Federico II, Italy
- 09:50 - Cellular and subcellular targeting of TRAP1 as a new therapeutic approach for cancer treatment
10:05 Clelia Mathieu, Institute Galien - Paris Sud, France
- 10:05 - Question and answer session
10:20
- 10:25 - Effects of cytokines release in tissue regeneration and cancer treatments
10:40 Slivia Pisani, University of Pavia, Italy
- 10:40 - Bacterial membrane vesicles as novel treatment avenue for intracellular infections
10:55 Gregor Fuhrmann, HIPS, Saarbrücken, Germany

Thursday, 13 May 2021

08:45 – 11:15	Invited talks	Short talks	Posters	Exhibition
11:15 – 11:45	Coffee break			
11:45 – 12:15	Award session			
12:15 – 13:15	Plenary lecture			
13:15 – 14:45	Lunch			
14:45 – 17:15	Invited talks	Short talks		

time zone
CEST

Invited talks: Formulation issues for biotech drugs incl. Q&A

Chairs: Chris van der Walle, GSK and Karoline Bechtold-Peters, Novartis

- 08:45 - Pellet freeze-drying of biopharmaceuticals
09:30 Stefan Schneid, Bayer, Wuppertal, Germany

Programme

10:55 - Question and answer session
11:10

Short talks: Continuous manufacturing / Modeling and simulation

Chairs: Joao Pinto, University of Lisbon and Martin Bornhöft, APV

08:45 - Characterization of a Continuous Small-Scale Solid-Liquid Separator for Filtration, Washing, and Drying of Pharmaceutical Suspensions
09:00 Claas Steenweg, University of Dortmund, Germany

09:00 - Continuous production of cyclodextrin-based reconstitution powder from aqueous solution using scaled-up electrospinning
09:15 Panna Vass, Budapest University of Technology and Economics, Hungary

09:15 - Question and answer session
09:30

09:35 - An in-silico workflow for designing a continuous mixing process with DEM simulations
09:50 Peter Toson, RCPE, Graz, Austria

09:50 - Visualization of solvent effects on crystal surfaces by chemical force mapping - a combined experimental and simulation approach
10:05 Mikkel Herzberg, University of Copenhagen, Denmark

10:05 - Question and answer session
10:20

10:25 - Predicting crystal breakage in pharmaceutical agitated dryers
10:40 Francois Hallac, University of Leeds, UK

10:40 - Dissolution and re-crystallization of supersaturated indomethacin solutions
10:55 Andreas Danzer, University of Dortmund, Germany

10:55 - Question and answer session
11:10

11:15 - 11:45 Coffee break/exhibition/posters

11:45 - 12:15 APV award session

APV Research Award 2019/2020: Olivia Merkel
APB Best Thesis Award 2019/2020: Flavia Fontana
EJPB Best Paper Award 2020

Plenary lecture incl. Q&A

Chair: Joerg Breitzkreutz, University of Düsseldorf

12:15 - Pharmacomicrobiomics: drugs meet the human microbiome
13:15 Christine Moissl-Eichinger, Medical University of Graz, Austria

13:15 - 14:45 Lunch break/exhibition/posters

Invited talks: Oral drug delivery incl. Q&A

Chairs: Robert O. Williams, University of Texas and Joerg Breitzkreutz, University of Düsseldorf

14:45 - Hydrophobic ion pairs: A game-changing approach for delivery of BCS class 3 drugs
15:30 Andreas Bernkop-Schnürch, Faculty of Chemistry and Pharmacy, University of Innsbruck, Austria

15:35 - Biological barriers to oral delivery of macromolecules
16:20 Caitriona O'Driscoll, School of Pharmacy, University of Cork, Ireland

16:25 - The virtual patient and the in-silico design of solid dosage forms
17:10 Hans Leuenberger, College of Pharmacy, University of Florida, Lake Nona Medical Campus, Orlando, FL, USA

Invited talks: Amorphous drug delivery systems incl. Q&A

Chairs: Susanne Page, Roche and Thomas Rades, University of Copenhagen

14:45 - Hybrid mixtures: A perspective on amorphous solid dispersions in food applications
15:30 Lennart Fries, Nestlé Research Center, Vevey, Switzerland

15:35 - Rational selection of Amorphous Solid Dispersion (ASD) Compositions for Improving Drug Candidate Bio-performance
16:20 David Lyon, Lonza, USA

16:25 - Talk to be determined
17:10 Speaker tbc

Short talks: 2D- and 3D-printing

Chairs: Milen Dimitrov, University of Sofia and Natalja Genina, University of Copenhagen

14:45 - Direct powder extrusion 3D-printing: novel technology for manufacturing amorphous solid dispersions
15:00 Alvaro Goyanes, FabRx, London, UK

15:00 - Semi-solid extrusion and alginate ionotropic gelation: a successful duo for the production of personalized floating formulations via 3D printing
15:15 Paola Russo, University of Salerno, Fisciano, Italy

15:15 - Question and answer session
15:30

15:35 - Selective laser sintering of solid oral dosage forms with copovidone and paracetamol using a CO₂ laser
15:50 Yanis Abdelhamid Gueche, University of Montpellier, France

15:50 - Direct-ink writing of implantable hybrid PCL/PEO drug delivery systems
16:05 Se Hun Chung, University College London, UK

16:05 - Question and answer session
16:20

16:25 - Investigations on inkjet printed metoprolol tartrate orodispersible films for paediatric application
16:40 Olga Kiefer, University of Düsseldorf, Germany

16:40 - Traceable personalized oral dosage forms containing cannabinoids
16:55 Natalja Genina, University of Copenhagen, Finland

16:55 - Question and answer session
17:10

Programme

Short talks: Skin delivery and protein formulations

Chairs: Nina Dragicevic, Singidenum University and Majella Lane, University College London

- 14:45 - A new approach to predict in vitro-in vivo correlation for transdermal therapeutic systems
15:00 René Rietscher, LTS Lohmann Therapie-Systeme, Andernach, Germany
- 15:00 - Proliposomes for the production of deformable liposomes containing drug micelles
15:15 Silvia Franze, Univeristy of Milan, Italy
- 15:15 - Question and answer session
15:30
- 15:35 - EPR study of effect of ascorbic acid on hair and feather samples in relation to eumelanins and pheomelanins
15:50 Michael Lawson, University of Bratislava, Slovakia
- 15:50 - α -relaxation studies to improve long term stability of lyophilized products from a thermodynamical point of view
16:05 Sebastial Groel, Univeristy of Munich, Germany
- 16:05 - Question and answer session
16:20
- 16:25 - Continuous alternative to freeze-drying: solid formulation of a monoclonal antibody using high-speed electrospinning
16:40 Júlia Domján, Budapest University of Technology and Economics, Hungary
- 16:40 - A holistic approach to develop a spray-drying method for CXCL8
16:55 Sonja Hartl, RCPE, Graz, Austria
- 16:55 - Question and answer session
17:10

- 09:35 - Digital Process Design
10:20 Sean Bermingham, Process System Enterprise (PSE), London, United Kingdom
- 10:25 - Study of the drying process in simulated pharmaceutical coatings: Model and experiment
10:40 Ondrej Navratil, University of Prague, Czech Republic
- 10:40 - In silico design of tablet microstructure by evolutionary algorithm
10:55 Frantisek Stepanek, University of Prague, Czech Republik
- 10:55 - Question and answer session
11:10 from the two short talks

Invited talks: Nanofabrication technologies incl. Q&A

Chairs: Claus-Michael Lehr, University of Saarbrücken and Maria Carafa, University of Rome

- 08:45 - Novel manufacturing for healthcare: microbubbles, particles, capsules and fibres
09:30 Mohan Edirisinghe, Biomaterials Processing Laboratory, Department Mechanical Engineering, University College London, United Kingdom
- 09:35 - Advances in electrospinning
10:20 Nalin de Silva, Department of Chemistry, University of Colombo, Sri Lanka
- 10:25 - Advanced in vitro lung-on-chip platforms for inhalation assays
11:10 Josue Sznitman, Department of Biomedical Engineering, Israel Institute of Technology, Haifa, Israel

Short talks: Gene delivery and ATMP

Chairs: Nathalie Mignet, University Paris Descards and Juan M. Irache, University of Navarra

- 08:45 - Formulation development to stabilize viral vectors
09:00 Julia Rabas, Leukocare, Munich, Germany
- 09:00 - Tablets of siRNA lipoplexes: impact of processes on structure and gene-silencing efficacy
09:15 Virgine Busignies, University of Bordeaux, France
- 09:15 - Question and answer session
09:30
- 09:35 - Anti-EGFR nanovector of siRNA - a theranostic tool for triple negative breast cancer active targeting
09:50 Phuoc Vinh Nguyen, Tours University, France
- 09:50 - siRNA in lung slices: knocking down fibrosis?
10:05 Mitchel Ruigrok, University of Groningen, The Netherlands
- 10:05 - Question and answer session
10:20
- 10:25 - mRNA based Skin Vaccination by intradermal application of lipid coated polymeric nanoparticles
10:40 Lena Kliesch, Helmholtz-Institute for Pharmaceutical Research Saarland, Germany
- 10:40 - MSC extracellular vesicles for treatment of alpha-1-antitrypsin deficiency pulmonary diseases
10:55 Elia Bari, University of Pavia, Italy
- 10:55 - Question and answer session
11:10

Friday, 14 May 2021

08:45 – 11:15	Invited talks	Short talks	Posters	Exhibition
11:15 – 11:45	Coffee break			
11:45 – 12:15	Award session		Posters	Exhibition
12:15 – 13:15	Plenary lecture			
13:15 – 14:45	Lunch		Posters	Exhibition
14:45 – 17:15	Invited talks	Short talks		

time zone
CEST

Invited talks: In silico simulation for manufacturing processes incl. Q&A

Chairs: Pierre Tchoreloff, University of Bordeaux and Peter Kleinebudde, University of Düsseldorf

- 08:45 - Digitalization in pharmaceutical product and process design: from advanced simulations to virtual drug product development
09:30 Johannes Khinast, Graz University of Technology, Austria

Programme

Short talks: Advanced drug delivery

Chairs: Olivia Merkel, University of Munich and Hendrik von Büren, AbbVie

- 08:45 - Repurposing of cationic amphiphiles to promote cytosolic RNA delivery
09:00 Koen Raemdonck, Ghent University, Belgium
- 09:00 - Alginate-spermidine microgels as filling matrix of multi-channel PLGA scaffolds for the treatment of peripheral nerve injuries
09:15 Caterina Valentino, University of Pavia, Italy
- 09:15 - Question and answer session
09:30
- 09:35 - Preparation and evaluation of anticancer agent nanocrystals
09:50 Yohann Corvis, University of Paris, France
- 09:50 - Evaluation of in vivo efficacy of ferrocifen loaded lipid nanocapsules on ovarian cancer
10:05 Elise Lepeltier, University of Angers, France
- 10:05 - Question and answer session
10:20
- 10:25 - A novel polyethylene glycol-based linker platform for the development of hydrophilic antibody-drug conjugates
10:40 Tommaso Tedeschini, University of Padova, Italy
- 10:40 - Dithiolane-crosslinked polymer micelles: reduction responsive drug release
10:55 Cornelus van Nostrum, University of Utrecht, The Netherlands
- 10:55 - Question and answer session
11:10

11:15 - 11:45 Coffee break/exhibition/posters

11:45 - 12:15 International ADRITELF Award 2020

Giuseppe De Rosa, University of Naples Federico II, Italy
Chair: Anna-Maria Fadda, University of Cagliari and Paolo Caliceti, University of Padova

Plenary lecture incl. Q&A

Chair: Anna-Maria Fadda, University of Cagliari and Paolo Caliceti, University of Padova

- 12:15 - Oral drug delivery systems: from irrelevance to top-selling products and ongoing challenges
13:15 Andrea Gazzaniga, Biopharmaceuticals and Pharmaceutical Technology Laboratory, University of Milan, Italy

13:00 - 15:00 Lunch break/exhibition/posters

Invited talks: Dermal and transdermal delivery incl. Q&A

Chairs: Paola Minghetti, University of Milan and Dominique Lunter, University of Tuebingen

- 14:45 - Skin permeation from Pickering emulsions
15:30 Marie-Alexandrine Bolzinger, Claude Bernard University Lyon, France
- 15:35 - Microarray patches for high-dose drug delivery: targeting global healthcare challenges
16:20 Ryan F. Donnelly, School of Pharmacy, Queen's University Belfast, United Kingdom

- 16:25 - Improved vaccine immunogenicity through microneedle delivery
17:10 Michael Schrader, Vaxess, Boston, MA, USA

Invited talks: Continuous manufacturing incl. Q&A

Chairs: Ali Rajabi-Siahboomi, Colorcon and Michael Repka, University of Mississippi

- 14:45 - Process development of the future: fully automated DoE process analysis in an integrated continuous manufacturing plant for solid oral dosage forms
15:30 Victoria Pauli, Novartis, Basel, Switzerland
- 15:35 - Residence Time Distribution (RTD) concept as element in drug product quality control strategies for continuous manufacturing
16:20 Bart Nitert, Janssen Pharmaceuticals, Beerse, Belgium
- 16:25 - Continuous manufacturing of solid dosage forms; opportunities and controversies
17:10 Kendal Pitt, GlaxoSmithKline, Ware, United Kingdom

Short talks: Oral drug delivery / Pediatric formulations

Chairs: Sandra Klein, University of Greifswald and Luigi Boltri, Adare

- 14:45 - The Use of Partially Hydrolysed Polyvinyl Alcohol for The Production of High Drug-Loaded Sustained Release Pellets via Extrusion-Spheronization and Coating: In Vitro and In Vivo Evaluation
15:00 Valerie Vanhoome, University of Ghent, Belgium
- 15:00 - X-ray imaging of microrcontainers used for oral drug delivery
15:15 Rolf B. Kjeldsen, Technical University of Denmark, Lyngby, Denmark
- 15:15 - Question and answer session
15:30
- 15:35 - Controlled permeability enhancement with short peptide inhibitors of protein kinase C zeta
15:50 Joel Brunner, University of Geneva, Switzerland
- 15:50 - A toolbox for mimicking gastrointestinal conditions in children: S(imulated) P(aediatric) B(reakfast) M(edia) for addressing the variability of gastric contents after typical paediatric breakfasts
16:05 Lisa Freerks, University of Greifswald, Germany
- 16:05 - Question and answer session
16:20
- 16:25 - Design and evaluation of self-emulsifying drug delivery system for pediatric use
16:40 Xiaona Liu, University of Copenhagen, Denmark
- 16:40 - Acceptability of antibiotics in pediatrics: findings from an international observational study
16:55 Thibault Vallet, ClinSearch, Malakoff, France
- 16:55 - Question and answer session
17:10

Short talks: Processing and PAT

Chairs: Javier O. Morales, University of Chile and Francisco Otero Espinar, University of Santiago de Compostella

- 14:45 - Improving flowability and reducing storage agglomeration of metformin hydrochloride through QESD crystallization
15:00 Jerome Hansen, University of Düsseldorf, Germany

Programme

- 15:00 - Production and downstream-processing of API-nanosuspensions
15:15 Arno Kwade, Technical University of Braunschweig, Germany
- 15:15 - Question and answer session
15:30
- 15:35 - Improving particle size distributions in a conical mill through new impeller air flow optimization comparisons utilizing computational fluid dynamics (CFD) analysis and empirical DoE
15:50 Wilf Sanguesa, Quadro Engineering, Ontario, Canada
- 15:50 - Innovative preparation of API salt coated on particles using fluidised bed
16:05 Jakub Muzik, University of Prague, Czech Republik
- 16:05 - Question and answer session
16:20
- 16:25 - Insight into the impact of compaction process variations on tablet disintegration by non-destructive at-line terahertz porosity sensing
16:40 Prince Bawuah, University of Cambridge, United Kingdom
- 16:40 - NIR as an in-line PAT tool to study desorption kinetics in spin freeze-dried formulations
16:55 Laurens Leys, Ghent University, Belgium
- 16:55 - Question and answer session
17:10
- 17:15 End of conference

Poster sessions

Wednesday, 12 May 2021

Nanoparticles and vesicles
Dermal preparations
Transdermal delivery
Protein formulation and aggregation
Gene delivery
Cellular drug transport
Parenteral delivery
Quality control and PAT
Quality assurance
Green and sustainable pharma

Thursday, 13 May 2021

Oral delivery
Controlled drug delivery
Advanced drug delivery systems
Advance therapy medicinal products
Technical innovations
Pediatric and geriatric drug delivery
Veterinary medicine
Packaging
Regulatory affairs

Friday, 14 May 2021

Pharmaceutical manufacturing and engineering
Bioavailability and absorption enhancement
In-vitro/In-vivo correlations
Stability testing
Preformulation
Physical pharmacy
Starting materials
Pulmonary delivery
Buccal and nasal delivery

Chairs and committees

Chair of the conference

Eva Roblegg, University of Vienna/University of Graz, Austria

Co-chairs of the conference

Jörg Breitzkreutz, University of Düsseldorf, Germany
Anna Maria Fadda, University of Cagliari, Italy
Jürgen Siepmann, University of Lille, France

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